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MYRTUS

Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems

Deliverable: **D11.3 - Dissemination and Communication Report v1**

Due date of deliverable: (30-06-2025)

Actual submission date: (30-06-2025)

Start date of Project: 01 January 2024

Duration: 36 months

Responsible: Andrés Otero (UPM)

Revision: draft

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
DEC		
SEN		

DOCUMENT INFO

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Document history

Document version #	Date	Change
0.1	22/05/2025	First Draft of D11.3
0.2	10/06/2025	Receive and integrate revisions 1 and 2
0.3	27/06/2025	Final version of D11.3

Document data

Keywords	Communication, Dissemination
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Funded by the European Union, by grant No. 101135183. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

1 Executive Summary	5
1.1 Related Documents	5
1.2 Structure of the Document	6
2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy	6
2.1 Communication and Dissemination Goals in MYRTUS	7
2.2 Identification of the Target Groups	8
2.3 Methodology for Communication and Dissemination	22
Branding and graphic design	22
Generation of Dissemination Materials	23
Continuous Feedback and Advice from Dissemination Activities	23
2.4 Open Access Policy	23
3 Digital Channels	24
3.1 Project Website	24
3.2 Partners' websites	24
3.3 Social Networks	26
4 Media and Press Releases	26
4.1 Traditional channels	26
4.2 Scientific press	26
5 Scientific Publications	27
5.1 Scientific Publications Plans	27
5.2 Conferences and Workshops	30
6 Fairs and Events	33
6.1 Participation in Fairs and External Events as a Consortium	33
6.2 Individual participation in other events	33
6.3 Organization of Events	34
7 Joint dissemination with other projects	35
8 Monitoring and Success Performance Indicators	36
9 Conclusions	37
10 References	37

1 Executive Summary

The deliverable D11.3 - Dissemination and Communication Report v1 is an R type (Document, Report), and, following the already submitted plan, it provides the first version of the reporting activities about dissemination and communication of the MYRTUS project. It includes all the activities covered in WP11 until month 18.

D11.3	WP	Lead	Type	Month
Dissemination and Communication Report	WP11 - Communication and Dissemination	UPM	R	M18

R: Report type

For completeness, it also quickly recalls the guidelines and the goals of the dissemination and communication plan already provided in D11.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan v1. The overall project strategy for protecting, disseminating, and exploiting results also includes additional aspects and actions related to exploitation and the open-source plan. These are interleaved with the actions reported in this document.

2 Introduction

This document presents the main dissemination and communication results achieved during the first 18 months of the project, evaluated against the Dissemination and Communication Plan. This plan represents the initial phase of an ongoing process that includes continuous monitoring of dissemination and communication outcomes, using a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) defined in the Grant Agreement (GA), as well as assessing partners' adherence to the plan. A new version of the plan (D12.4) will be provided by Month 22, considering the results at the end of Phase 1 of the project, the feedback from the first review, and contributions from third parties, including communities and other initiatives. Then a final version of the present Dissemination and Communication Report (D11.5) will also be provided at M36, offering a coherent strategy to impact the target communities effectively, also in the mid and long term after the project completion.

As an initial summary, it can be highlighted that the MYRTUS partners have already:

1. Set up the entire infrastructure for communication and dissemination, including the project website, social accounts (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.),
2. published (or received the notification of acceptance) of 13 peer-reviewed papers at conferences and 3 journals,
3. participated in more than 20 leading events of the CPS community, presenting tutorials and giving lectures at summer schools, and
4. been actively involved in dissemination events organized by the MYRTUS brother and sister projects.

Please note that only the activities related to external communication channels are reported in this document. Internal communication within the consortium follows the channels and tools described in the *Project Quality Handbook*, along with the procedures established at the coordination and management levels.

[Table 1 – Deliverable D11.2- Dissemination and Communication Plan v1](#)

D11.2- Dissemination and Communication Plan v1 – M8 – Tasks Involved: T11.1 (M1-M36) - Communication [SOFT(L), ALL] T11.2 (M1-M36) - Dissemination [UPM(L), ALL]
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2.1 Related Documents

This deliverable closely relates to the following documents:

- **D13.1 - Project quality handbook:** Includes the templates for generating dissemination material, the logos, and the internal communication tools, among others.
- **D11.1 – Project website and social media account:** Describes the channels for reaching the MYRTUS target audience and objectives, including traditional approaches, such as the project website and social media (LinkedIn, X, and YouTube). These tools will be of significant importance for the project's C&D activities.
- **D12.2 - Exploitation, Standardisation, and Open Source Plan v1:** Exploitation and dissemination activities are closely related, being addressed together thoroughly, in WPs 11 and 12.
- **D11.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan v1:** Presents the general C&D strategy for the project.
- **D11.3 - Exploitation, Standardisation and Open Source Rep v1:** Offers a complementary report to this one, describing the exploitation activities carried out during this period.

2.2 Structure of the Document

The rest of this deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 3: Summary of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy** - Provides an overview of the high-level communication strategy, setting the goals, the target groups, and the methodology that will guide the whole plan.
- **Chapter 4: Completed Dissemination and Communication Activities** - This section summarizes the activities performed to support communication by the MYRTUS consortium
- **Chapter 5: Digital Channels for MYRTUS Dissemination** - Including websites and social networks.
- **Chapter 6: Media and Press Releases** - Including traditional channels and non-scientific press.
- **Chapter 7: Scientific Publications** – Ranging from journals to conferences and workshops.
- **Chapter 8: Fairs and Events** - Both at the consortium and partner levels. Particular emphasis will be put on events organised by the MYRTUS partners.
- **Chapter 9: Joint Dissemination with Other Projects** - actions are described to foster collaborations with other brother and sister projects funded by the HORIZON Europe call "*Cognitive Computing Continuum: Intelligence and Automation for More Efficient Data Processing*".
- **Chapter 10. Monitoring and Success Performance Indicators** - Describes the updated list of metrics used to follow the evolution of the KPIs associated with the C&D actions of the project. They are used to monitor the evolution of the adherence of the project partners to the C&D plan.

3 Summary of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy

In this section, we summarize the dissemination and communication strategy planned in D11.2. The main goal of the MYRTUS project is to effectively disseminate the MYRTUS activities and results across all target groups. To guarantee the success of these activities, a strategic plan has been designed, including all the required measures to ensure that C&D activities align with the project goals and the detailed actions and resources needed to implement the C&D strategy effectively. Andrés Otero (UPM) is responsible for coordinating and overseeing these activities, leading the Communication and Dissemination work package. Abisula, as project coordinator, and UNICA, as technical coordinator, provide strong support for all activities related to this aspect of the project. Notably, there is also close collaboration with Alessandra Bagnato (SOFTEAM), who is in charge of the project’s Exploitation, Standardisation, and Open Source initiatives, activities that are fully complementary to communication and dissemination.

The communication and dissemination actions outlined in this plan focus on sharing information about the project and its results with scientific, industrial, and societal audiences. In MYRTUS, dissemination and communication activities are strictly linked to exploitation, and the overall targets are illustrated in Figure 1. Some of these targets (“switched off” in the figure) are primarily exploitation targets, and communication and dissemination actions towards them are meant mainly for the use of results. The rest of the targets (“highlighted” in the figure) are primarily dissemination and communication targets.

Figure 1- MYRTUS dimension highlighting main dissemination and communication targets.

As a reminder of the C&D plan presented in D11.2, the objectives for the C&D activities in MYRTUS are the following:

- At the Scientific level:
 - Create new knowledge in the computing continuum domain, with methodologies and tools for node execution and processing portability over edge-fog-cloud, including dynamic and seamless orchestration.
 - Become a reference in the computing continuum.

- Follow-up research and projects beyond MYRTUS.
- At the economic and technological level:
 - Overcome vendor/platform lock-in.
 - 15 external startups and SMEs adopt MYRTUS technologies, reducing development time and cost.
 - MYRTUS industrial partners enrich their business offerings and attract key world-leading partners.
- At the social level:
 - Induce positive changes of habit in society through human-centred CPS.
 - Guarantee capillarity rehabilitation services and equitable access to care.
 - Decrease mortality on the road by making intersections safer.
 - Contribute to the CO2 emission reduction.

4 Completed Dissemination and Communication Activities

This section summarizes all the activities performed from M1 to M18 to support communication by the MYRTUS consortium.

The common visual identity has been defined and reported in the *Project Handbook* and is available for all the partners in the shared repository, together with the associated templates. The project logo is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2- MYRTUS Logo.

In addition, ABINSULA has established the online Dissemination **Communication and Exploitation shared tool**, which is a shared Excel file to monitor all the communication and dissemination activities carried out in the project. It measures the impact associated with the action, such as the target audience and the number of attendees. Figure 3 shows a view of the current status of the tool.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Added to the participant portal	Status (Under Review / Accepted / Rejected)	Partner(s)	Type of PID* (for most publication will be DOI)	PID* (publisher version of record) - for most publication it will be the DOI	PID* of deposited publication	Type of Publication *	Link to publication deposited in Zenodo (or other open repo)	Date of publication in Zenodo (or other open repo)	Title*
2	Yes	Accepted	ALL	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1145/3631743.3654618	10.1145/3631743.3654619	Publication in Conference proceedings/Works hop	https://zenodo.org/records/11143736	8 May 2024	MYRTUS: Multi-layer 360° dynamic orchestration and interoperable design environment for compute-continUum
3	Yes	Accepted	UNISS, UNICA	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-78380-7_7	https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.09078	Publication in Conference proceedings/Works hop	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13918433	13 June 2024	ONNX-to-Hardware Design Flow for Adaptive Neural-Network Inference on FPGAs
4	Yes	Accepted	TUD	DOI	10.1109/FDL63219.2024.10673834	10.5281/zenodo.13888296	Publication in Conference proceedings/Works hop	https://zenodo.org/records/13888297	7 October 2024	Timing enclaves for performance in Lingua Franca
5	Yes	self-publish	TUD	DOI	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.11898	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.11898	Other	https://zenodo.org/records/13888678	27 June 2024	E-Mapper: Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation for Traditional Operating Systems on Heterogeneous Processors
6	Yes	Accepted	USI	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1145/3629938.3694775	https://doi.org/10.1145/3629938.3694775	Publication in Conference proceedings/Works hop	https://zenodo.org/records/13939652	14 Oct 2024	Energy Analysis of Cryptographic Algorithms in Server Environment
7	No	Accepted	SOFT	DOI	XXXX	10.5281/zenodo.13889626	Publication in Conference proceedings/Works hop	https://zenodo.org/records/13889626	4 October 2024	Towards Model-based System Engineering for Cyber Physical Systems in the MYRTUS project.

Figure 3- General view of the communication and exploitation shared tools.

5 Digital Channels for MYRTUS Dissemination

The actions carried out by the MYRTUS consortium through digital channels are gathered in this section.

The MYRTUS website (<https://myrtus-project.eu/>), as outlined in deliverable D11.1, was set up at month 3 to serve as the central hub for all project activities, including public deliverables, publications, and other tangible results. Enhanced with high-quality visual design and illustrations, the website makes MYRTUS more engaging and memorable. Since its creation, access to the website has been monitored with a proper analytics tool. In the last month before the deliverable finalization, the website has received around 1267 visitors (traffic sessions).

Figure 4 - MYRTUS Website.

A considerable effort has also been carried out to ensure that the catalog of tools and components is already available on the website, with the appearance shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Overview of the MYRTUS Results already included in the website.

Most of the partners have also used the websites of their respective organizations to announce the kick-off of the project. A list with some of the links is provided in Table 1.

Table 1 – Link to MYRTUS on each partner website.

Partner	Announcement on the website
ABI	Inclusion in the list of research projects on the Abinsula website: https://abinsula.com/myrtus/
TUD	Since the start of MYRTUS, the project has been listed on the website of the Chair for Compiler Construction at TUD, under “Major Collaborations”: https://cfaed.tu-dresden.de/cc-collaborations
UNISS	Publication of the KO Meeting on the institutional website: https://www.uniss.it/it/eventi/progetto-horizon-europe-myrtus
UNISS	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the institutional website https://www.uniss.it/it/ricerca/finanziamenti-la-ricerca/finanziamenti-europei/progetti-di-ricerca-europei
UNICA	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the MeDSP Lab website https://sites.unica.it/medsp/projects/
KCL	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the institutional website: https://www.kcl.ac.uk/news/kings-engineer-awarded-horizon-europe-grant-to-build-connected-future-for-healthcare-and-smart-cities
SOFT	Inclusion in the list of research projects on the Softam R&D website: https://www.softeam-rd.eu/projects/myrtus-multi-layer-360-dynamic-orchestration-and-interoperable-design-envi

LAKE	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the organisational website: https://www.lakeside-labs.com/research/projects-and-funding/
CRF	Inclusion in the list of research projects on the CRF website: https://www.crf.canon.fr/AboutCRF_en.html
UPM	Reference to the face-to-face General Assembly celebrated in Madrid: https://www.industriales.upm.es/noticias/asamblea-general-del-proyecto-myrtus/

Social media channels, particularly LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter), were established in Month 2 of the project. To foster engagement, we are publishing monthly posts highlighting the project's technical developments, often aligned with the release of relevant publications. This initiative is referred to as **Myrtus Shots**, and an example is shown in Figure 7. Posts generating significant interaction are expanded into longer LinkedIn articles, with a target of producing 3–4 such articles annually. While X is used to broaden outreach beyond LinkedIn's professional audience, the consortium has agreed to prioritize LinkedIn as the main communication platform. X will be maintained as a complementary channel to amplify content originally shared on LinkedIn.

Figure 6 - Main page of the Myrtus LinkedIn Profile.

Figure 7- Example of a Myrtus Shot.

The MYRTUS page in **LinkedIn** has **368 followers**, it had **20.580 Impressions in the last 365 days**, and an iteration rate of 12,75% (average, last 12 months), with 75 published posts. The X MYRTUS account in the period has achieved 86 followers, with 67 published posts.

MYRTUS is aligned with the Open Science principles promoted by the European Commission, which improve the diffusion of generated knowledge and data, foster open cooperative work, and maintain a solid adherence to the FAIR principles [1]. As derived from these principles, scientific publications in MYRTUS will follow the Open Access guidelines for Horizon Europe to ensure transparency of the processes and outcomes of research and disseminate new knowledge to foster open science.

In this regard, we have created the MYRTUS community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/myrtus/>). All partners are committed to sharing their publications through this tool (agreed in the GA celebrated in July 2024, in Madrid).

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for the MYRTUS community. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The community name 'MYRTUS - Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmT for compute-continUum Systems' is displayed, along with a 'New upload' button. Below this, there are filters for 'Records' and 'Members'. The main content area shows 15 results found, sorted by 'Newest'. Two records are visible:

- Record 1:** 'Key Enabling Technologies for Cognitive Computing Continuum - MYRTUS Project Perspective' by Palumbo, Francesca; Ratto, Francesco; Rubattu, Claudio; and 5 others. It is a 'Conference paper' from January 7, 2025, with 15 versions. The description mentions it is an accepted version for the DATE 2025 conference.
- Record 2:** 'Leveraging Incremental Machine Learning for Reconfigurable Systems Modeling under Dynamic Workloads' by Otero, Andrés; Encinas, Juan; and Rodríguez, Alfonso. It is a 'Publication' from January 7, 2025, with 14 versions. The description discusses dynamic workload orchestration in edge-cloud environments.

Figure 8 - MYRTUS Community in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/myrtus/records>.

A total of 21 dissemination and communication results are already available for public access in this repository.

6 Media and Press Releases

6.1 Traditional channels

Traditional media is considered to inform society beyond the scientific community, reaching a more general audience. MYRTUS consortium agreed to promote the submission of press releases coinciding with relevant events in the project, such as the Kick-off Meeting, or the intermediate and final project events. An example is the following press article published after the kick-off:

- **Article on the Sardinina regional paper "La Nuova Sardegna"**, to announce the kick off of the MYRTUS project. Partners Involved: ABI, UNICA, UNISS. Date: 6/2/2024

6.2 Scientific press

MYRTUS also decided to target non-scientific magazines generally addressed to academic and industrial communities. In particular, two main magazines have already been identified:

- **Inside Magazine:** This magazine targets the INSIDE Industry Association (IA) community. It is generally promoted through the INSIDE's digital channels and is mainly distributed in digital form. However, during physical events organised by INSIDE, hard copies of the Magazine are also available. **Contributions related to MYRTUS have already been published in the INSIDE IA Magazine #6 (February 2024)¹ and #7 (June 2024)². Partners involved: ABI, UNICA.**
- **HiPEAC Info:** The HiPEAC Info magazine is a quarterly publication providing the latest news on the activities within the European HiPEAC network, as well as activities on high-performance embedded architectures and compilers at large. The magazine is sent to more than 500 researchers from academia and industry, and company managers in Europe, America, and Asia.

Besides, two more releases in the scientific press have been achieved during this period:

- MYRTUS Brochure for **New Projects in AI, Data, and Robotics 2024 Edition. 22/2/2024.**
- **Interview given to the Italian Electronics Society**, published on their blog, aimed at discussing cutting-edge technologies and inspiring the next generation to pursue a career in Electronic Engineering. **MYRTUS has been provided as an example of a challenging research project in the field.** 15/05/2025. Partner involved: UNICA

¹ <https://intranet.inside-association.eu/publication/download/inside-magazine-6.pdf>

² <https://intranet.inside-association.eu/publication/download/inside-magazine-7.pdf>

7 Scientific Publications

The actions related to scientific publications are reported in this section. **At the M18 of the project, there are 3 journal papers, and 13 conference papers accepted, targeting very diverse communities, from HPC, to Embedded, EDA Tools, or microelectronics, among others.** The complete list of accepted submissions is listed below. Five of these publications are already a joint effort between consortium partners.

7.1 Scientific Publications

The following journal publications of MYRTUS results have been achieved up to M18 of the project:

Journals

1. LIN, Shaokai, et al. Navigating Time and Energy Trade-offs in Reactive Heterogeneous Systems. *IEEE Embedded Systems Letters*, 2024. Partner (s): TUD – Keywords: Compiler, concurrency, design space exploration (DSE), energy consumption, quasi-static scheduling – Target Community: EDA.
2. ENCINAS, J., RODRIGUEZ, A., OTERO, A. (2025). Leveraging Incremental Machine Learning for Reconfigurable Systems Modeling under Dynamic Workloads. *ACM Transactions on Reconfigurable Technology and Systems*, 18 (1), 1-27. Partner (s): UPM – Keywords: Multi-Accelerator Systems, Reconfigurable Computing, Dynamic Workloads, Incremental Machine Learning, System Modeling – Target Community: Embedded, Microelectronics.
3. RUBATTU, C, et al., Integrating FPGA-based Acceleration in Industrial Motion Control System, *IEEE Open Journal of the Industrial Electronics Society*. Partner (s): UNICA, UNISS – Keywords: Field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs), high-level synthesis (HLS), industrial motion control systems, multiprocessor systems on chips (MPSoCs), systems on module (SoMs) – Target Community: Embedded.

Conferences and Workshops

1. PALUMBO, Francesca, et al. MYRTUS: Multi-layer 360 dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers (CF24): Workshops and Special Sessions*. 2024. p. 101-106. Partner (s): ABINSULA, UNICA, UNISS, Softeam, TUD, TNO, LAKE, UPM, HIRO, KCL, FRS, ArubaKube, CRC, UaV, USI – Keywords: Computer hardware and architecture, Design environment, Dynamic orchestration, Computing continuum, Interoperability, AI – Target Community: Embedded, EDA.
2. MANCA, Federico; RATTO, Francesco; PALUMBO, Francesca. Onnx-to-hardware design flow for adaptive neural-network inference on FPGAs. In *International Conference on Embedded Computer Systems: Architectures, Modeling, and Simulation, SAMOS 2024*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024. p. 85-96. Partner (s): UNICA, UNISS – Keywords: Convolutional Neural Networks, Approximate Computing, FPGAs, Cyber-Physical Systems – Target Community: Embedded, HPC.

3. ROBLED, Julian, et al. Timing enclaves for performance in Lingua Franca. In *2024 Forum on Specification & Design Languages (FDL 2024)*. IEEE, 2024. p. 1-9. Partner (s): SOFTEAM – Keywords: Baseband, Runtime, Scheduling algorithms, Computational modeling, Semantics, Parallel processing, Real-time systems – Target Community: Artificial Intelligence for CPS, Model-based system engineering for CPS.
4. THAKUR, Sushmita; BANIK, Subhadeep; REGAZZONI, Francesco. Energy Analysis of Cryptographic Algorithms in Server Environment. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Cloud Computing Security Workshop*. 2024. p. 3-14. Partner (s): USI – Keywords: Block Ciphers, Energy Consumption, Intel RAPL – Target Community: Security.
5. BAGNATO Alessandra; CADAVID Juan.; Towards Model-based System Engineering for Cyber Physical Systems in the MYRTUS project. *Challenges and New Approaches for Dependable and Cyber-Physical System Engineering (DeCPS 2024)*, co-located with the 28th Ada-Europe International Conference on Reliable Software Technologies (AEiC 2024). Partner (s): SOFTEAM – Keywords: Cyber Physical Systems, CPS, Requirements Engineering, AI, model-driven engineering. – Target Community: Model-based system engineering for CPS.
6. DE ULZURRUN, Iñigo Díez, et al. Cloud-Edge Continuum Infrastructure for Reconfigurable Multi-Accelerator Systems. In *2024 39th Conference on Design of Circuits and Integrated Systems (DCIS)*. IEEE, 2024. p. 1-6. Partner (s): UPM – Keywords: Cloud computing, Scalability, Circuits, Microservice architectures, Benchmark testing, Hardware, Resource management, Virtualization, Distributed computing – Target Community: Embedded, Microelectronics.
7. BI, Jiahong; KOROL, Guilherme; CASTRILLON, Jeronimo. Leveraging the MLIR infrastructure for the computing continuum. 2024. CPS Workshop 2024. Partner (s): TUD – Keywords: Computing continuum, Domain Specific Language, Compiler Optimizations – Target Community: Embedded.
8. PALUMBO, Francesca, et al. Key Enabling Technologies for Cognitive Computing Continuum - MYRTUS Project Perspective. Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference 2025 (DATE 25), Lyon, France. Partner (s): UNICA, UNISS, TNO, ABINSULA, TUD, HIRO – Target Community: Embedded, EDA.
9. BANIK, Subhadeep; REGAZZONI, Francesco. Faster and more energy-efficient equation solvers over GF (2). En *International Conference on Security, Privacy, and Applied Cryptography Engineering (SPACE 2024)*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024. p. 16-39. Partner (s): USI – Target Community: Security
10. WU, Kefan; GHASEMI, Abdorasoul; SCHRANZ, Melanie. Swarm Intelligence-Based Algorithm for Workload Placement in Edge-Fog-Cloud Continuum. En *17th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence*. 2024. p. (In-Press). Partner (s): LAKE – Keywords: Swarm Intelligence, Edge-Fog-Cloud Continuum, Ant Colony Optimization. – Target Community: Swarm intelligence.
11. VARZONOVA, Nadeshda; SCHRANZ, Melanie. COSMOS: A Simulation Framework for Swarm-Based Orchestration in the Edge-Fog-Cloud Continuum. In *15th International Conference on Simulation and Modeling Methodologies, Technologies and Applications (SIMULTECH)*. Partner (s): LAKE – Keywords: Agent-Based Simulation, Edge-Fog-Cloud Continuum, Swarm Intelligence – Target Community: Swarm intelligence.
12. ENCINAS Juan et al., Modular and Composable Framework for Multipurpose Monitoring in Heterogeneous FPGA-Based Systems. In the proceedings of the *25th International Conference on Embedded Computer Systems: Architectures, Modeling*

and Simulation (SAMOS XXV). Partner (s): UNICA, UNISS, UPM – Target Community: Embedded, HPC

13. MANCA F., et al., Runtime Reconfigurable FPGA Accelerator for Tactile Texture Classification Based Shallow CNN, 20th International Conference on PhD Research in Microelectronics and Electronics (PRIME). Partner (s): UNICA – Target Community: Embedded, Microelectronics.

Self-published in arXiv:

1. SMEJKAL, Till, et al. E-Mapper: Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation for Traditional Operating Systems on Heterogeneous Processors. arXiv preprint, arXiv:2406.18980, 2024. Partner (s): TUD – Target Community: Programming Languages.
2. KOROL G. et al. , Leveraging Stochastic Depth Training for Adaptive Inference, arXiv preprint, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.17626>. 2025. Partner (s): TUD – Keywords: Edge Computing, Adaptive Inference, CNN – Target Community: Programming Languages.

Articles in CF24 and DATE25 were part of special sessions targeting European projects, **where the evolution of the consortium as a whole was presented**. These conferences, and others such as DSD (Special session on European and Major Multi-Partner Projects in Digital Systems Design), will also be tracked in the following editions, to continue with this joint dissemination effort.

8 Fairs and Events

8.1 Participation in Fairs and External Events as a Consortium

MYRTUS has been promoted at eight major events, targeting communities and specialized audiences, engaging approximately 580 participants. Besides, two tutorials were performed, and MYRTUS researchers have participated in multiple Webinars, Workshops, Seminars, and Round Tables related to the project. A detailed list of events is provided below:

Collaboration with EU-funded projects:

1. **ECS Brokerage Event 2024.** As the winner of the 2024 RIAs Challenge, MYRTUS presented a poster at the ECS Brokerage 2024 to give an overview of the whole project (objectives, challenges, and plans). Dates: 20/02/2024 – 21/02/2024. Brussels. Organized by ENEAS, EPoSS, and INSIDE. Target Audience: Research communities, Industry, business partners, and EU Institutions. Around 500 academic and industrial experts. Partners Involved: ABI, UNICA.
2. **Launch Event: Showcasing the future of innovation in AI, Data, and Robotics.** Give an overview of the whole MYRTUS project (objectives, challenges, and plans). MYRTUS Project presentation. Organized by Adra-e, AI on Demand, and the European Commission. Date: 22/02/2024. Targeting: Research communities. Partners Involved: ABI, UNICA.
3. **NexusForumEU.** Panel session on "The CognitiveCloud as a Key Enabler for DataSpaces". Target Audience: "Industry, business partners", Research communities, Other. Date: 19.09.24 - 20.09.24. Belgium. More than 200 registrations for the event. Partners Involved: SOFTEAM.
4. **NexusForumEU.** Panel session on "MYRTUS, a Computing Continuum Ecosystem Leveraging AI Technologies". Target Audience: "Industry, business partners", Research communities, Other. Date: 19/09/24 – 20/09/24. Belgium. More than 200 registrations for the event. Partners Involved: SOFTEAM.
5. **Discover US Webinar.** Giving a webinar with the title "Unlocking nature's secrets: Engineering cyber-physical systems with swarm intelligence". Target Audience: Research Communities. Organized by Discover US. Around 45 attendants. Date: 10/10/2024, Recording: <https://youtu.be/T8VMT5O4LIQ>, Partners Involved: LAKE.
6. Participation in the **DISCOVER-US workshop**, a networking event to start defining the main content of a white paper on computing continuum technologies. Organized by Discover US Consortium. Date: 24/06/24 -26/06/24, Target Audience: Partners Involved: UNICA.
7. **Challenges and New Approaches for Dependable and Cyber-Physical System Engineering (DeCPS 2024).** The MYRTUS project was presented with a focus on current SOFT activities on modelling. Target Audience: Research communities, Industry, and business partners. 14/06/2024 – 14/06/2024, Barcelona. Partners Involved: SOFTEAM. Other projects present:
8. **Challenges and New Approaches for Dependable and Cyber-Physical System Engineering (DeCPS 2025).** The MYRTUS project was presented with a focus on current SOFT activities on modelling. Target Audience: Research communities, Industry, and business partners. 13/06/2025, Paris. Partners Involved: SOFTEAM.

Companies' engagement:

9. **Le PMI in Horizon Europe: Dall'idea al mercato** - Presentation of the MYRTUS project as a successful use case, in the context of innovation action related to SMEs. Target: Research communities, Industry, business partners, Regional authorities, Local authorities, and Citizens. Date: 25/09/23. Cagliari. Organized by Sardegna Ricerche - APRE. Around 20 participants. Partners Involved: ABI, UNICA.

Education and training events:

10. **5th Summer School on Cyber Physical Systems and Internet of Things.** Lecture on UNISS-UNICA activities in MYRTUS, with a hands-on session (tutorial) related to Adaptive CNN execution on edge FPGAs. Around 40 attendants. Target: Research communities, "Industry, business partners", Date: 11/04/2024 – 14/04/2024, Budva. Organized by: Mediterranean Embedded Computing. Partners Involved: UNISS, UNICA.
11. **6th summer school on CPS from concepts to implementation.** MYRTUS concepts and UNICA+UNISS were presented to the audience, with a hands-on session (tutorial) related to Adaptive CNN execution on edge FPGAs. Target Audience: Research communities. 16/09/2024 – 20/09/2024. Alghero. Around 45 attendants. Partners Involved: UNICA, UNISS.
12. Juan Encinas from UPM held a **Seminar, within the department of electronics at UNICA, to create awareness of MYRTUS results.** Target Audience: Research communities. 10/12/2024. Partners Involved: UPM, UNICA.
13. Juan Encinas from UPM held a **Seminar, within the department of electronics at UNICA, open to the students pursuing their Master's on Embedded Systems, to create awareness of MYRTUS results.** Target Audience: Higher Education Students and Young Researchers in training. 13/12/2024. Partners Involved: UPM, UNICA.
14. Seminar for the students of the Bachelor's in Computer Engineering at the UNISS. **Awareness of MYRTUS activities for encouraging participation through these and internships.** Target Audience: Higher Education Students and Young Researchers in training. - Date: 18/12/2024 Partners involved: UNICA, UNISS.

Conferences and Workshops:

15. **21st ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers.** Presented the paper: Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum. Target Audience: Research communities. Partners Involved: USI, UPM, All. Date: 08/05/2024. Ischia. Organized: ACM.
16. **European Test Symposium 2024.** Presented the Paper: "Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems" The Hague. 20/05/2024 – 24/05/2024. Target Audience: Research communities. Partners involved: USI.
17. **SAMOS XXIV.** UNICA and UNISS presented a toolchain part of the MYRTUS DPE to researchers of the embedded systems community. Research communities, "Industry, business partners". 29/07/2024 – 4/08/2024. Samos, Greece. Partners involved: UNISS, UNICA.
18. **2nd Sino-European Workshop on Opportunities and Cooperation in Computer Architecture.** Presentation: "General Purpose Reconfigurable Accelerators for RISC-V. Extensions for safety-critical Applications". MYRTUS project was presented with focus on UPM activities on MLIR for CGRAs. Research Communities. 27/11/2024 –

- 30/11/2024. Hong Kong, China. Organized by Hong Kong Institute of Science and Innovation, Chinese Academy of Sciences. Partners involved: UPM.
19. **The 42nd IEEE International Conference on Computer Design (ICCD 2024).** Presentation at DCIS 2024 of the paper "Cloud-Edge Continuum Infrastructure for Reconfigurable Multi-Accelerator Systems" related to the use of reconfigurable nodes in the MYRTUS infrastructure. Target Audience: Research communities. 13/11/2024 – 15/11/2024. Catania. Organized by IEEE. Partner involved: UPM.
 20. **Dagstuhl Seminar 25091:** "Tradeoffs in Reactive Systems Design". 23/02/2025 – 28/02/2025. Wadern, Germany. Organized by: TUD (with UC Berkeley, ONERA, University of Manouba). Partner involved: TUD.
 21. **Workshop Challenges and New Approaches for Dependable and Cyber-Physical System Engineering.** MYRTUS project presentation with focus on current SOFTTEAM activities on modelling. Target Audience: Industry Business Partners. 13-06/2025 – 13/06/2025, Partner involved: SOFTEAM.
 22. **Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference (DATE 2025)** - Presentation on the workshop "W07 Designing Sustainable Intelligent Systems: Integrating Carbon Footprint Reduction, TinyML, and RISC-V" with a talk entitled "W07.3 MYRTUS: Advancing Sustainable and Secure Computing with RISC-V". 31/03/2025 – 02/04/2025. Lyon, France. Partner involved: UPM.
 23. **Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference (DATE 2025)** - Presentation of the PhD thesis of Juan Encinas in the PhD forum, with title "ML-based resource management of reconfigurable systems in the cloud-edge continuum". TARGET: Research Communities. 31/03/2025 – 02/04/2025. Lyon, France. Partner involved: UPM.
 24. **Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference (DATE 2025)** - Presentation of MYRTUS activities in Multi-partner projects session. TARGET: Research Communities. 31/03/2025 – 02/04/2025. Lyon, France. Partner Involved: UNICA.
 25. **RISC-V Summit Europe.** Presentation of the poster "Integration of a CGRA Accelerator with a CVA6 RISC-V Core for the Cloud-edge". Target Audience: Research communities. 12/05/2025 – 15/05/2025. Paris, France. Partner involved: UPM
 26. **IEEE 31st International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Innovation (ICE IEEE/ITMC2025)** Participation in the Cognitive Computing Continuum session. 16/05/2025 – 19/05/2025. Valencia, Spain. Target Audience: Research communities. Partner Involved: UPM.

The distribution of the principal events in time is represented in Figure 9.

Figure 9 - Timeline of the MYRTUS Activities targeting Communities and Specialized Audience .

Apart from the events in which MYRTUS has already been presented, the consortium maintains the commitment to celebrate the final scientific event at HiPEAC and a final

industrial event at Embedded World, as stated in the communication and dissemination plan for the project. The intermediate event at the CPS Summer School is currently being organized, as reported in the next section.

8.2 Individual Participation in Other Events

These events are especially relevant, since they target the general audience:

1. **Long Night of Research, Austria.** Presentation of the MYRTUS project with a focus on swarm intelligence application in the edge-fog-cloud continuum. Around 8000 participants attended the event. Date: 24/05/2024. Target Audience: Civil society, Citizens. Austria. Organized by: Austrian Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology. Partner involved: LAKE
2. **Notte Europea dei Ricercatori e delle Ricercatrici (European Researchers' Night).** MYRTUS project presentation with a focus on current UNICA-EOLAB activities. Target Audience: Civil society, Citizens. Date: 27/09/2024. Cagliari. Organized by UNICA as part of the SHARPER project. Partner involved: UNICA.
3. **Open Source Experience (OSXP 2024).** MYRTUS was presented on the 5th December 2024 by Alessandra Bagnato to the Open Source Experience audience in Paris. The event is supported by Systematic Paris-Region. Open Source Experience is the Tech – Usage – Business event dedicated to Open Source IT solutions, bringing together over 4,000 professionals and players in the digital sector, Open Source Experience focuses on open source technologies, solutions and challenges in France and Europe, and highlights the driving role of open source innovations in the digital transformation of organisations in technologies such as AI, Data Management, IoT, Cloud and Blockchain. As an international showcase for the technological excellence and economic dynamism of the French open source sector, the event brings together global technology players, professional associations, companies and public authorities, a vast network of SMEs and research bodies. Partner involved: SOFTEAM.

8.3 Organization of Events

Most of the dissemination actions and events in this plan involve multiple partners, highlighting the collaborative nature of the MYRTUS project. Additionally, some partners are involved in organizing long-standing events, providing excellent opportunities to engage with well-established communities that may find MYRTUS results valuable.

Especially relevant for the Communication and Dissemination actions of the project will be the **Myrtus Intermediate Event, co-located with the International CPS Summer School.** The International CPS Summer School is an annual one-week event that targets students, research scientists, and R&D experts from academia and industry who want to learn about CPS engineering and applications. The school started in 2017 and covers all the design phases of CPSs, starting from the conception of the idea down to the definition of the final system and will discuss the key challenges (including adaptivity support, modelling, and security), presenting state-of-the-art tools and methods, also allowing participants to play with industrial and academic design environments. Lectures and tutorials are given by academics (e.g., Prof. Alberto Sangiovanni-Vincentelli, UC Berkeley, Prof. Hironori Kasahara, Waseda University, Prof. Nikil Dutt from UC Irvine) and industrial speakers (e.g., Dr Danilo Pau,

STMicroelectronics, Dr. Paolo Azzoni, Eurotech/INSIDE). The director of the School since its origin is Prof. Francesca Palumbo, and almost all editions so far have taken place in the north of Sardinia.

In 2024, the school took place in Alghero, in the facilities of the University of Sassari, and apart from Prof. Palumbo. Also, Prof. Francesco Regazzoni (USI), Prof. Mauro Fadda (UNISS), Dr. Claudio Rubattu (UNISS), Dr. Francesco Ratto (UNICA), Prof. Andres Otero (UPM), and Juan Encinas (UPM) from the MYRTUS consortium were involved in the organisation committee. Dr. Claudio Rubattu (UNISS) and Dr. Francesco Ratto (UNICA), with the support of Dr. Federico Manca, gave a tutorial titled “Adaptive CNN execution on edge FPGAs,” which involved the technologies jointly developed by UNISS and UNICA in WP3 and WP7. Moreover, UNICA, UNISS, and UPM teams coordinated the creative lab, which was specifically meant to train the school attendees on FPGA technologies at the edge.

The technical program of the 2025 edition of the school (<https://www.cpsschool.eu/program/>) will involve **four different slots dedicated to MYRTUS technologies** and given by our partners:

- Hands-on TOSCA designer given by SOFT
- Working flow example and demonstration on Edge-Fog Continuum and Resource Orchestration given by UNISS, UPM, UNICA, ARK, and ABI.
- Lecture on “Unlocking nature’s secrets: Swarm Intelligence in CPS” by Dr. Melanie Schranz (LAKE).
- Presentation of the MYRTUS project by Prof. Francesca Palumbo (UNICA).

Moreover, we also expect **submissions and presentation** of different works carried out by PhD students involved in MYRTUS **to the CPS workshop** that is a traditional initiative of the CPS Summer School to offer participants a close contact with leading experts on the field, as well as the opportunity to present and discuss their ideas in a dynamic and friendly setting.

Finally, for the year 2025, the **MYRTUS Intermediate event** will be co-located with the school. UNICA and ABI are currently organizing the event, which will involve all the school participants, the consortium partners, and also other invited external people. The goal will be to showcase MYRTUS technologies through demonstrators and gather feedback on the actual developments.

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
	<i>Introduction</i>	<i>Modelling and Design</i>	<i>Architectures</i>	<i>Security on CPS</i>	<i>Creative Lab Day</i>
8:15-8:50	Registration and Opening				
8:50-9:00		Opening	Opening	Opening	Opening
9:00-10:30	Nikil Dutt (UC IRVINE)	Edoardo Charbon (EPFL)	Alberto Sangiovanni Vincentelli (UC Berkeley)	Laura Pandolfo (UNISS)	Creative Lab @ Work
10:30-11:00	Break	Break	Break	Break	Break
11:00-12:30	Melanie Schranz (LAKESIDE)	MYRTUS tutorial TOSCA Designer	Mladen Berekovic (UNI-LUEBECK)	SECURED tutorial Privacy Preserving	Creative Lab @ Work
12:30-13:30	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch panel: career development	Lunch	Lunch
13:30-14:00	Creative Lab Presentation	Creative Lab @ work	MYRTUS tutorial Resource Orchestration (13:30 - 15:00)	Creative Lab @ work	Creative Lab Pitch & Demo
14:00-15:30	CPS - WORKSHOP Pitch presentation (14:00 - 15:00)	Michele Magno (ETH)		Elif Bilge Kavun (UNI PASSAU)	
15:30-16:20	MYRTUS project presentation (15:00 - 15:30)		Creative Lab @ work (15:00 - Till you'd like)		
	Aperitif with CPS WS Poster Session & MYRTUS intermediate event (19:00 - 21:00)	Beach note - Alberto Sangiovanni-Vincentelli Bus from Piazzale della Pace (leaves at 17:30) Beach Note (18:15-19:15) Pizza @ La Palafitta (19:30-22:30) Bus to Piazzale della Pace (leaves at 22:30)		Social dinner Bus from Piazzale della Pace (leaves at 18:30) Dinner (19:00-23:00) Bus to Piazzale della Pace (leaves at 23:00)	Farewell Toast (starting at 16:30)

Figure 10 - Scheduling for the 2025 CPS Summer School, with all the activities related to MYRTUS highlighted.

The workshop Challenges and New Approaches for Dependable and Cyber-Physical System Engineering. co-located with the Ada-Europe International Conference on Reliable Software Technologies (AEiC), was co-organized by Softeam in 2024 and 2025. In 2024 the DeCPS 2024³ workshop was co-organized by SOFTEAM in Barcelona, Spain with a MYRTUS presentation titled “Towards Model-based System Engineering for Cyber Physical Systems in the MYRTUS project “ and in 2025 DeCPS 2025⁴ was co-organized by Softeam in Paris, France, the workshop Challenges and New Approaches for Dependable and Cyber-Physical System Engineering (DeCPS 2025) has been held on 13 June 2025, Paris, France and was Co-located with the 29th Ada-Europe International Conference on Reliable Software Technologies (AEiC 2025), the following presentation was given “A Model-based Cloud-Edge-Fog Applications Design walkthrough with the MYRTUS project’s Modelio TOSCA Designer “.

CEI Annual Meeting: The CEI annual meeting (UPM) is a two-day meeting focused on relevant technology trends (e.g., “Open Hardware & RISC-V” for the 2022 edition,” Challenges in

³ <https://www.ada-europe.org/conference2024/decps.html>

⁴ <https://www.ada-europe.org/conference2025/decps.html>

Microelectronics” for 2024) that hosts: 1) workshops/tutorials on hot topics (e.g., “Building custom RISC-V Systems on Chip with open-source tools”); 2) keynote and/or round tables (e.g., with members of the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre and the National Microelectronics Institute); 3) technical sessions, poster sessions, and networking occasion of their research activities. The last event was organised in May 2025, with more than 100 participants from companies and other universities, mainly from Spain. All the students involved in MYRTUS participated with a poster, and MLIR activities by UPM were included in one of the oral presentations.

Lakeside Research Days: The bi-annual Lakeside Research Days (LAKE) is a four-day workshop on topics like self-organisation in particular fields of application. Limited to 50 participants, including invited experts, local professors, and young researchers, discuss and elaborate ideas in the field of Self-Organizing Systems. The main emphasis of the workshop is on soliciting discussions and creating new ideas regarding topics related to self-organising systems. The event greatly supports scientific exchange, networking, the establishment of international collaborations, and joint research projects. The following video gives a nice impression of the Research Days: <https://youtu.be/3DPas4L1ov0>

The next event will take place in July 2026. The organisation will start in autumn 2025, with the umbrella topic “Swarms in Industry”. Regarding MYRTUS, the 360° vision of the architecture and how this consideration benefits from swarm intelligence approaches will be presented.

Reply XChange: The XChange event by Reply is an annual conference organised by Reply that focuses on technological innovation, digital transformation, and emerging trends in the IT sector. This event serves as a significant platform for industry professionals, clients, partners, and technology experts to gather, share knowledge, and discuss the latest advancements and best practices. The event features presentations by industry leaders, technology experts, and senior managers, offering insights on current topics and future perspectives. Attendees can participate in hands-on workshops and interactive sessions where they delve into specific technological topics, experiment with new solutions, and engage in discussions. Live demonstrations of innovative projects and technological solutions developed by Reply and its partners showcase practical applications and case studies, providing real-world context to the discussions. Networking opportunities abound, allowing attendees to meet, exchange ideas, and establish professional connections with peers, industry experts, and representatives from partner companies. Additionally, the expo area features exhibition spaces where partner companies and sponsors present their products and services, offering further opportunities for discovery and interaction.

Overall, the XChange event by Reply is a key event for anyone interested in technological advancements and innovation, providing a stimulating environment for learning, collaboration, and the development of new business opportunities.

9 Joint Dissemination with Other Projects

HYPER-AI project⁵: This project, funded in the same call of MYRTUS, aims at overcoming network continuum challenges by integrating smart virtual nodes from the cloud, edge, and IoT to optimise intensive data processing. Its goal is to revolutionise big data processing applications with self-abstracted and self-coordinated cloud-to-edge resources and it also fosters the co-creating of technologies and tools for the cognitive computing continuum. For this reason, HYPER-AI is promoting actions to join the efforts of 7 different EU projects (HYPER-AI, INTEND, EMPYREAN, ENACT, MYRTUS, Swarmchestrade, and COGNETs) funded by the HORIZON Europe call "*Cognitive Computing Continuum: Intelligence and Automation for More Efficient Data Processing*" to promote the use of the edge-cloud Continuum as a secure, autonomous, reliable, and self-managing computing resource. MYRTUS has been invited to participate in the following webinar: **Get to know the research initiatives about Cognitive Computing Continuum: Intelligence and automation for more efficient data processing**⁶. The webinar aimed to highlight the collaborative efforts and breakthroughs in integrating the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum, AI-driven resource management, and hyper-distributed computing ecosystems. MYRTUS will contribute by presenting its three main technical pillars.

⁵ <https://hyper-ai-project.eu/>

⁶ <https://hyper-ai-project.eu/events/webinar-get-know-research-initiatives-about-cognitive-computing-continuum-intelligence>

10 Monitoring and Success Performance Indicators

The KPIs for the C&D activities were already included in the proposal and confirmed in the Grant Agreement, from which the following table is extracted. This plan will maintain the same goals as the target. Please, notice that **Period 1** refers to “*During the project + 1 year*”, and **Period 2** refers to “*Period 1 + First 5 years after project end*”.

Table 2 presents the achieved results at the mid-point of the project, along with a comparison, both in absolute terms and percentages, **against the expected targets for Period 1**. Overall, the project's activity in website traffic, social media engagement, and participation in dissemination events has been intensive, with results surpassing expectations at this stage. Regarding video content, focused effort will now be directed toward its development, as integration activities and demonstrator setups by project partners progress. Scientific contributions are already substantial, targeting a variety of research communities and demonstrating strong collaboration across the consortium. Based on current progress, we are confident that the KPIs outlined in Table 2 for Period 1 will be met by the end of the period or shortly after the project closure, with no significant risks anticipated at this time.

Table 2 – KPIs for the different MYRTUS C&D Tools

C&D Tool	Key Performance Indicators			Achieved after M18
	Period 1 (Expected)	Period 2 (Expected)	Verification	
Project's Website	7500 page views	13000 page views	Google Analytics	1267 Sessions (16,9%)
Social Media Presence	300 posts 600 followers	400 posts 1200 followers	Social media analytics	Posts: 75 published in LinkedIn + 67 in X. (47% for Period 1) Followers: 368 in LinkedIn + 86 in X. (75% for Period 1)
Videos	10 YouTube videos, 500 visualisations	5000 visualisations	YouTube analytics	1 YouTube video with 125 visualizations. (10% of the videos, 25% of visualizations)
Promotional material in digital and hardcopy form	1000 recipients (digital and hardcopy)	2000 recipients (only digital)	Project reporting	NA yet.

Publications in scientific journals/ conferences	50 articles 75 citations	250 citations	Google Scholar, Scopus, DBLP	18 Scientific publications. (36% for period 1) Citation numbers are not relevant for the first half of the project.
Official EU Key Tools. Articles in EU magazines.	Use of the 4 Key Tools. 3 articles published at EU magazines	6 articles published at EU magazines.	Project reporting	Use of Zenodo (25% for the Period 1) 2 articles published in EU magazines. (66% for the Period 1)
Project public events*	3 physical events 30 attendees*	--	Project reporting	NA yet.
Partner public events	3 physical events 30 attendees*	30 events 30 attendees*	Project reporting	3 Events (Long Night of Researchers in Austria, Opens Source Experience, and Notte Europea dei Ricercatori e delle Ricercatrici with more than 8000 participants to the overall event) (100% for the Period 1)
External events participation	40 physical events 30 attendees*	60 events 30 attendees*	Project reporting	29 events 30 participants on average (72,5% for the Period 1)

* Average number of attendees per event

11 Conclusions

MYRTUS partners have made solid progress in communicating and disseminating MYRTUS activities and results. Key accomplishments include establishing a unified visual identity, launching the project website and social media channels, publishing the project kick-off, delivering the initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, and building a presence on Zenodo.

Multiple scientific outputs, including publications, papers, and theses, have been generated, and the project has been actively promoted at national and international events. From the perspective of communication and dissemination, the project is on track, and the expected impacts for Period 1 remain achievable.

12 References

- [1] [Open Data, Software and Code Guidelines | Open Research Europe \(europa.eu\)](https://europe.europa.eu/en/open-research/europe)